

Ibragimov Elshad Agaveli

Doctor of Philosophy in Biology. Assistant

Musayeva Leyla Bahtiyar

Department of Pediatric Dentistry Assistant

Arkhammammadova Gulshan Mubariz

Department of Orthopedic Dentistry. Assistant

Azerbaijan Medical University

Baku, Azerbaijan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15011496>

APPLICATION OF ULTRASONIC SYSTEMS IN ENDODONTICS

Abstract

High-quality endodontic treatment of tooth root canals is the most important stage of successful dental treatment. In dentist practice, there are situations when the canal lumen is blocked by an anchor pin. The situation is even more complicated if the tooth was previously treated with the resorcinol-formalin method. Currently, the use of an ultrasonic device and the availability of new endodontic attachments make it possible to quickly and effectively solve complex problems of repeated endodontic treatment with the removal of a foreign body and filling material from the lumen of the root canal.

Key words: *repeated endodontic treatment, ultrasonic device.*

Despite the existing progress in achieving effective results in the treatment of caries complications, the failure rate, especially in long-term follow-up, remains high. Thus, according to the European Association of Endodontists, the success rate of primary treatment is only 80%. The American Endodontic Association indicates only 53 - 80% success rate for treating pulpitis. Russian dentists (Borovsky E.V. et al., 1998) presented absolutely dismal results of treatment of pulpitis: after 3-4 years, only 29% of teeth do not have periapical lesions. It can be assumed that in Belarus this figure will not differ significantly. Another problem is the lack of motivation for endodontic treatment. If A treatment, 2) their capabilities for re-treatment of the tooth, 3) the need and possibility of conservative surgical treatment methods, 4) planning subsequent orthopedic treatment. The problems that the dentist encounters when starting to re-treat a tooth are most often associated with A. They are, as a rule, very labor-intensive and not feasible in every clinical case. The advent of ultrasound in endodontics is a new technology that combines traditional principles of treatment of the root canal system with ultrasound, biological, chemical and physical effects. Ultrasound systems in endodontics, for example (Suprason P-Max, Satelec), represent an easy and comfortable technology that allows the dentist to carry out almost all the main stages of endodontic treatment: quick and effective cleansing of the root canal system, its disinfection and rinsing, and, finally, filling it in three dimensions. Having received a diagnostic radiograph and assessed the clinical situation as the possibility and necessity of re-treatment of the tooth, the doctor begins the first stage - opening access to the root canals. Knowledge of the anatomy of the tooth and the topography of the canal mouths allows you to avoid mistakes and complications not only at this stage, but also creates the necessary conditions for the use of ultrasonic files in the root canal. Careful probing with hand-held thin instruments is necessary to find at least a narrow space in the canal that will serve as a guide for advancing the ultrasound files. It is relatively easy to detect if there is

a soft filling material (paste) in the canal. It is much more difficult to determine the lumen in the canal after a resorcinol-formalin mixture or in the presence of a fragment of an instrument or filling material. It should be remembered that such canals are infected and there is always a risk of the canal contents being pushed into the periodontium, which leads to pain after the intervention. An initial determination of the working length of the root canal is not always possible, especially if there is a foreign body in it. If it was possible to measure the length of the canal, then it is better to prepare the apical third with hand instruments No. 6-25, using them with lubricants (Canal+) and sodium hypochlorite (Parcan). And after that, start working with ultrasonic (US) files on the working length of the canal. Please note that they come in two types: ultrasonic K-files and ultrasonic diamond files. Diamond particles (fine and coarse) have the exceptional ability to conduct ultrasound energy, and the high elastic hardness of diamond makes it the best cutting material. Thanks to constant irrigation during the scoring process, ultrasonic diamond files are disinfected and self-cleaning. As a result, there is no blocking of the uneven diamond coating by particles of the filling material and dentin, and the instrument retains all its qualities. Diamond ultrasonic files are intended for preparation of only the coronal and middle third of the root canal. Therefore, after manual processing of the apical third, they begin to work with ultrasound K-files, sequentially changing their numbers from smaller to larger, depending on the lumen of the canal. The technique for working with ultrasound files is simple and controlled. First, the file is inserted and withdrawn (with a small - 1 mm - amplitude of movement along the axis of the tooth) for quick and effective cleaning. When working with such movements of the file, you should be extremely careful in a curved canal. An oscillatory lateral motion is then applied to rapidly align the canal. And, finally, at the final stage - rotational movements along the walls of the canal to give it a cone shape. The operating time for each file does not exceed 1 minute. It is well known that

work with any endodontic instrument must be accompanied by abundant rinsing to prevent blocking of the apical foramen and disinfection of the canal. In practice, this stage of endodontic treatment is underestimated and rarely performed in full. The Suprasson P-Max ultrasonic endodontic system allows you to do this very effectively. A flow-through irrigation system (a container with Parcan solution) is attached to the tip, and the solution, passing through it, washes the file from all sides. Ultrasound activates the irrigant and ensures their penetration into the complex canal system with its numerous branches, removing all organic particles. This ability is ensured not only due to the activation of the irrigation solution, but also due to the “explosive” and vacuum effect formed in the “ultrasonic” bath inside the channel. The problem of a smear layer on the canal walls after mechanical processing is also known. It closes infected dentinal tubules for access of antiseptics, preventing their complete cleansing. The same layer, rich in organic substances, is formed during ultrasonic treatment with irrigation with distilled water. Therefore, today it is considered rational and effective to use a combination of ultrasound and sodium hypochlorite, which removes the organic component of the smear layer, which leads to the opening of the dentinal tubules, and subsequently to the greatest adhesion of the filling material to the canal walls. It is also interesting that under the influence of ultrasound the temperature of sodium hypochlorite increases, which increases its activity, and in combination with the effect of cavitation leads to the destruction of the membrane of microorganism cells, their nuclei and enzyme systems. The number of bacterial populations decreases to zero 6 minutes after the start of work with ultrasound files (Martin H., 1980). This combined action is especially important when preparing the medial canals of lower molars, which have a complex system of intercanal spaces, connections, as well as lateral canaliculi. Taking into account the abundant irrigation with sodium hypochlorite solution during ultrasonic preparation, the dental unit should be equipped with a good suction system, and endodontic treatment should be carried out in 4 hands. Knowledge of the topography of the tooth root and root canals is mandatory for any technology of their preparation, including ultrasound. It should be remembered that care must be taken when working with ultrasound files in canals with thinned, anatomically concave walls, since due to the high efficiency of ultrasound exposure and the high cutting ability of ultrasound files, rapid perforation of the canal walls is possible. There is no need to put much effort on the file; a light touch of the canal walls is quite enough to achieve the expected result. A more complex manipulation is the removal of a foreign body from the canal using ultrasound. In this case, it is necessary to use thin hand files to detect or create free space between the canal wall and the instrument fragment. The introduction of an ultrasound file into this lumen and sounding of the fragment contributes not only to the expansion of free space due to the removal of dentin, but also to the “loosening” of the fragment, and sometimes its fragmentation. After removing the instrument, further prep-

aration of the canal is carried out according to the described method. The presence of special (long and short) attachments in the set greatly facilitates the removal of filling material, including gutta-percha, from the canal. In this case, work is carried out without irrigation after specially adjusting the power of the device. In this case, the gutta-percha softens and is easily removed from the canal. Hardening filling materials (pastes) are removed from the canal under constant irrigation. In difficult cases (phosphate cement), alternate work in the canal is carried out using manual and ultrasonic files until success is achieved. Removing metal inlays from the root canal is practically impossible without the use of ultrasound. Using an acoustic wave using a special file No. 20, 40, it is possible to destroy the filling material around the perimeter of the tab, loosen its hold in the canal and remove it using forceps. Such work requires maximum attention and delicacy in order to avoid complications (perforation, root crack), since the walls of the canal prepared for the stump insert are significantly weakened (Fig. 5). After completing the root canal preparation, it is dried with paper points and obturation begins. Modern ultrasonic endodontic systems have a special mode and devices for performing the final stage of treatment. As with any other method of filling a root canal, its walls must be lubricated with a sealer (for example, Acroseal Endometason N). It is to lubricate, and not to fill the lumen of the canal. This can be done using a hand K-file or a gutta-percha point. Then the master pin is inserted into the root canal and obturation is performed using an ultrasonic plugger. The ultrasonic plugger sinteres and compacts gutta-percha due to thermoacoustic effects and mechanical vibration. Ultrasonic vibration generates heat, which allows you to heat the gutta-percha pin and turn it into a homogeneous mass. The softened gutta-percha condenses in the canal. Thanks to this filling technology, all lateral branches of the canal are effectively filled, obturation occurs in three dimensions. As the channel is filled (by 1/2 of its length), additional pins are inserted into its lumen, as with the vertical condensation technique. Then the excess pins are cut off, and the gutta-percha is softened and compacted with an ultrasonic plugger, filling the entire lumen of the canal. Clinical observations of the results over three years of treatment of apical periodontitis using ultrasound to prepare the canal for filling showed the high effectiveness of this method. We monitored the treatment (clinically and radiologically) of 127 root canals of single- and multi-rooted teeth. A year later, 120 of them showed a decrease in foci of destruction and osteoporosis. In 7 cases, teeth were removed on the recommendation of an orthopedic doctor within 2 to 6 months after treatment. After 2–3 years, in 11 cases, minor symptoms of osteoporosis, widening, and periodontal fissures in the area of curved roots were noted. In 109 cases, there was a complete absence of clinical and radiological signs of inflammation of the apical periodontium

Conclusion: The use of ultrasound systems in endodontics has significantly expanded the dentist's ability to achieve success in repeat endodontic treatment.

The use of ultrasound as an effective method for preparing the root canal system, its disinfection and obturation has a great future

References

1. Gutman D.L. Povtornoje jendodonticheskoe lechenie s pomoshh'ju instrumentov sistemy ProTaper. Stomatologicheskij vestnik, № 5, – 2009.

2. Rouds Dzh. Povtornoje jendodonticheskoe lechenie. Konservativnye i hirurgicheskie metody. M., MEDpress-inform, 2009. – 216 s.

3. Shumskij A.V. Sovremennye ul'trazvukovye tehnologii v stomatologii. Stomatologija segodnja, № 7(67). – 2007